

CHURG-STRAUSS SYNDROME: A CASE REPORT

متلازمة شيرغ شتراوس: تقرير حالة طبية

Abdallah Khoury, MD; Fatima Alhamed Alduihi, MD

د. عبد الله خوري، د. فاطمة الحامد الضويحي

ملخص الحالة

متلازمة شيرغ شتراوس هي التهاب يصيب الأوعية المتوسطة والصغيرة الحجم من الشرايين والأوردة، وصفت هذه المتلازمة لأول مرة لدى 13 مريضاً لديهم قصة ربو متفاقم مع علامات متلازمة الربو، كثرة الإيوزينيات، التهاب الأنف والجيوب مع أعراض التهاب الأوعية في القلب، الشغاف، الجهازين العصبي والهضمي وبقيّة الأعضاء الحيوية. تعتبر الرئة هي العضو الأكثر إصابة في سياق هذه المتلازمة. سيتم في التقرير التالي عرض حالة من هذه المتلازمة عند امرأة سورية بعمر 29 سنة، راجعت بارتشاحات رئوية مزدوجة مع إنتانات تنفسية ناكسة، تحسنت بالمعالجة بالستيروئيدات القشرية والسيكلوفوسفاميد.

ABSTRACT

Churg-Strauss syndrome (CSS) is a vasculitis of medium to small sized muscular arteries and veins. CSS was first described in 13 patients with deadly asthma who had the combination symptoms of asthma and eosinophilia, rhinosinusitis and signs of vasculitis in the heart, pericardium, the nervous and gastroenteric systems and other vital organs. Lung is the organ most frequently involved. We describe the case of a 29-year-old Syrian woman with bilateral pulmonary infiltrations and recurrent respiratory infections, which has been improved by corticosteroids and cyclophosphamide.

INTRODUCTION

Churg-Strauss syndrome was first described in 1951 by Churg and Strauss.¹ Churg-Strauss syndrome (CSS) is a systemic vasculitis involving medium to small vessels, affecting several organs.² It was first described in 13 patients with deadly asthma who had

the combination symptoms of asthma and eosinophilia, rhinosinusitis and signs of vasculitis in the heart, pericardium, the nervous and gastroenteric systems and other vital organs.^{1,3} Actually, this disease is renamed to eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis (EGPA).⁴ Usually the patients' age range is between 20 and 40 years, and both men and women are equally affected.² Lungs are the organs most frequently involved, followed by kidneys.²

Most reports consider this vasculitis a disease by itself or a variant of asthma which occurs from immune system involvement such as with the use of medications like leukotrienes or sudden withdrawal of oral steroids.^{3,5,6}

They also consider environmental factors significant in development of primary systemic vasculitides.⁷ One of these factors is the influence of severe antigenemia (SAg) in inducing vasculitis.^{3,6,8} Presumptively inhaling allergens, vaccination, desensitizing medications and

*Abdallah Khoury, MD, CESAEU. Professor in the Department of Pulmonary Diseases, Aleppo University Hospital, Aleppo, Syria.

*Fatima Alhamed Alduihi, MD, Resident in the Department of Internal Medicine, Aleppo University Hospital, Aleppo, Syria. E-mail:dr.duihi88@hotmail.com.

even infections and Loeffler's syndrome can behave as a triggering event against T-lymphocytes and cause the signs of CSS in the asthmatic population.^{7,9,10}

Epidemiology: CSS is a rare disease. The annual incidence of CSS in Olmstead County, Minnesota, was estimated to be 4/1,000,000 inhabitants based on a single case seen during the period from 1976 to 1979.^{1,3} From 1988 to 1998, 14 cases of CSS were diagnosed in the Norwich Health Authority.^{1,4}

Diagnosis: We have 3 diagnostic criteria classification, and nomenclature of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis during the last 20 years.

According to Lanham's criteria all three criteria must be met for a diagnosis of EGPA: asthma, peak peripheral blood eosinophil count $>1.5 \times 10^6/\text{cc}$ and systemic vasculitis involving two or more extrapulmonary organs.^{11,12} According to the American College of Rheumatology (ACR), there are four or more criteria out of six for the diagnosis: asthma, eosinophilia ($>10\%$ in peripheral blood), paranasal sinusitis, pulmonary infiltrates, histological evidence of vasculitis with extravascular eosinophils, and mononeuritis multiplex or polyneuropathy.¹³

According to Revised International Chapel Hill consensus conference nomenclature of vasculitides (2012), Eosinophil-rich and necrotizing granulomatous inflammation often involving the respiratory tract, and necrotizing vasculitis predominantly affecting small to medium vessel, and associated with asthma and eosinophilia. ANCA is more frequent when glomerulonephritis is present.¹¹

Table 1 summarizes the three diagnostic criteria.¹¹ Pulmonary eosinophilia can be due to large number of diseases as varied as allergic disorders, parasitic, fungal infections, vasculitis, drugs, lymphoma, idiopathic etc.¹⁴ We will discuss a state that we diagnose CSS by biopsy after we make a lot of procedures that are been mentioned in the article. Anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibodies (ANCA) are important serological markers for certain

small-vessel vasculitides, encompassing Wegener granulomatosis (WG), microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) and Churg-Strauss syndrome (CSS).¹⁵ French and Italian clinical studies found that the clinical characteristics of patients with Churg-Strauss syndrome differed according to their antineutrophil cytoplasmic autoantibody status: cardiomyopathy predominated in antineutrophil cytoplasmic autoantibody-negative patients while necrotizing glomerulonephritis was more often observed in antineutrophil cytoplasmic autoantibody-positive patients.¹⁶

CASE PRESENTATION

A 29-year-old Syrian woman has been admitted with a story of productive cough with purulent expectoration without blood traces, worsening of dyspnea and fatigue with a fever in the past month. In addition to increased shortness of breath, the patient developed gradual paresthesia in her left lower leg. She coursed dysphasia and weight loss (about 9 kg in six months).

On physical examination, she was in respiratory distress and had coarse crackles and generalized ronchi and wheezing in the lung bases. The level of SPO_2 upon admission was 74% and increased to 91% with administration of 6 liters of 40% oxygen via venturi mask.

A complete blood count showed a white cell count (WBC) of 22300 with 1.6% eosinophils, 85.7% neutrophils and 6.4% monocytes. Her Hb was 10.8 g/dl and the platelets count was 261000 per cubic millimeter. Renal function tests, blood coagulation studies and electrolytes were within normal limits. Urinalysis was normal. The liver tests show a little increasing in total bilirubin, while other liver tests were around normal limits.

Her immunology tests for liver were normal and also tumor markers (alpha fetoprotein, CA19.9 and CEA). Tests for rheumatoid factor (RF), anti nuclear antibodies (ANA), circulating anti-neutrophil cytoplasmic antibody (cANCA), perinuclear anti-neutrophil

cytoplasmic antibody (pANCA) as well as C3, C4 were negative. USG abdomen was normal. No hepatomegaly or splenomegaly, no ascites or lymphadenopathy. Echocardiography was also normal, no regurgitation or stenosis of valves, and the left ventricular function was normal. EMG (electromyography) and NCV (nerve conduction study) studies showed neuritis and axonopathy along the common peroneal nerve located below the left knee level.

The chest X-ray showed bilateral infiltrations. Sputum for AFB was negative. Stool examination did not reveal any ova or cyst.

Chest computed tomography (CT) demonstrated the presence of multiple pulmonary nodules, consolidation and ground glass opacities, raising the diagnostic hypotheses of Wegener granulomatosis and Churg Strauss syndrome. The pleural biopsy suggests vasculitis.

Fiber optic bronchoscopy revealed inflammatory

mucosa and we take a bronchoalveolar lavage for PCR test and for cytological examination. Mycobacterium Tuberculosis (Real Time) PCR was also negative.

Cytological examination of bronchial smears and washings show moderately cellular smears with benign ciliated respiratory epithelial cells, many neutrophils, some macrophages, small lymphocytes, and few buccal squamous cells. Bronchoalveolar lavage (BAL) revealed neither mycobacteria nor cancerous cells, Figure 1 and Figure 2.

A Needle renal biopsy was done, composed of three renal parenchymal cylinders comprising cortical and medullary areas with fibrous renal capsule, 77 glomeruli are seen reveal normal architecture and normal cellularity in most of them, some reveal increase in the number of mesangial cells, no crescents are seen.

The tubules and interstitium are normal. The blood vessels are unremarkable, Congo red stain was negative for amyloid deposit. The histological changes on the

Lanham diagnostic criteria (1984) ^a	American college of rheumatology classification criteria (1990) ^b	Revised International Chapel Hill consensus conference nomenclature of vasculitides (2012)
Asthma	Asthma	Eosinophil-rich and necrotizing granulomatous inflammation often involving the respiratory tract, and necrotizing vasculitides predominantly affecting small to medium vessel, and associated with asthma and eosinophilia. ANCA is more frequent when glomerulonephritis is present.
	Eosinophilia (>10% of total WBC)	
Blood eosinophilia >1500/mm ³ or >10% of total WBC		
	Pulmonary infiltrates non-fixed	
Evidence of vasculitis involving two or more organs	Paranasal sinus abnormalities	
	Extravascular eosinophils	

a. All three criteria must be met for a diagnosis of EGPA, b. The presence of four or more of these six criteria yielded a sensitivity of 85% and a specificity of 99.7% for the classification of vasculitis as EGPA, WBC, white blood cells.

Table 1. Diagnostic criteria, classification, and nomenclature of eosinophilic granulomatosis with polyangiitis during the last 20 years.

Figure 1. Moderately cellular smears with benign ciliated respiratory epithelial cells, many neutrophils, some macrophages, small lymphocytes, and few buccal squamous cells.

Figure 2. The arrow refers to an eosinophils.

ground of light microscopic are those of focal mesangio-proliferative GN. An incisional lung biopsy from left lung shows focal aggregation of inflammatory cells forming variable size nodules within the pulmonary parenchyma (subpleural and interstitial nodules), these nodules composed of neutrophils, eosinophils and histocytes, very few multinucleated giant cells and rimmed by fibroblasts. PAS stain was negative and Zheil Nelson too. The histological changes consistent with Eosinophilic granuloma of the lung.

During her hospital stay, our patient was treated with oral steroids and cyclophosphamide, and she was discharged two weeks after admission in no respiratory distress and good general health.

DISCUSSION

ANCA associated vasculitis (AAV) includes EGPA,

Eosinophilic pneumonia (chronic or acute)
Hypereosinophilic syndrome
Bronchocentric granulomatosis (allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis)
Wegener granulomatosis
Miscellaneous

Table 2. Eosinophilic pneumonia (chronic or acute).

microscopic polyangiitis (MPA) and granulomatosis with polyangiitis (GPA).^{17,18} The cause of Churg-Strauss syndrome is unknown, but its characteristic histological findings and association with asthma distinguish it from other vasculitides.¹⁹ Etiology is considered to be autoimmune due to allergic symptoms, immune complex mediation 48% are (ANCA, antineutrophil cytoplasmic antibody) positive, increased T-cell mediated immunity, elevated immunoglobulin E (IgE) levels and rheumatoid factor.⁹

Clinical diagnosis is based on American College of Rheumatology Criteria which requires the presence of four or more of the six conditions: asthma, eosinophilia >10%, neuropathy, migratory or transient pulmonary opacities, abnormalities of the paranasal sinuses and extravascular eosinophils on biopsy. Regularly, a history of asthma and rhinosinusitis precedes the appearance of the syndrome itself.²⁰ Histological diagnosis is by demonstration of vasculitis that is necrotizing, tissue infiltration with eosinophils and extra-vascular granulomas are found in a few cases.^{5,21}

The classic pathologic findings in the lung include a combination of eosinophilic pneumonia, granulomatous inflammation, and vasculitis.²²

Diagnosis often requires careful correlation of the clinical and pathologic findings. Differential diagnosis of

Churg-Strauss syndrome in the lung includes: eosinophilic pneumonia (chronic or acute), hyper-eosinophilic syndrome, broncho-centric granulomatosis (allergic bronchopulmonary aspergillosis), Wegener granulomatosis, miscellaneous (infections, dirofilarial nodules, eosinophilic vascular infiltration of pneumothorax), Table 2.²² Radiological differential diagnoses include disorders associated with prominent eosinophilic infiltrate or a combination of granulomatous with eosinophilic inflammation.^{1,22,23}

Treatment regularly is with prednisone starting at 40-60 mg a day and the occasional addition of cyclophosphamide or azathioprine with the purpose to limit the disease or spare steroids.

CONCLUSIONS

Even though the Churg-Strauss syndrome is rare in medical field, but it must be in suppose in front of any double infiltrations in patients with a story of productive cough even pANCA and cANCA are negative.

Consent: Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this manuscript and any accompanying images.

Authors' contributions: AK and FD participated in planning of case reporting and provided case presentation and guidance and manuscript was prepared by two authors. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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